

RADx-UP Community Collaboration Grant Program: A Summary of TSBM Outcomes

The Community Collaboration Grant Program (C2G) has funded 69 projects across 7 funding cycles.

Translational Science Benefits Model¹

IMPACT PROFILE

The Impact

The C2G funded projects resulted in clinical, community & public health, policy and economic benefits.

Through community health services, training, and education projects increased access to and uptake of diagnostic COVID-19 testing in communities of underserved and vulnerable populations.

The Challenge

Communities across the United States are disproportionately impacted by COVID-19, with many underserved and vulnerable communities' facing barriers to COVID-19 testing and diagnosis.

COVID-19 testing, isolation, contact tracing, among others, in communities will help decrease COVID-19 transmission and save lives.

The Approach

C2G provides Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) subawards to increase the capacity for COVID-19 testing expertise within the community. Increasing training, education, communication, information dissemination, and capacity building related to COVID-19 testing, isolation, contact tracing, among others, in communities will increase our ability to decrease COVID-19 transmission and save lives.

The goal of the program is to improve access to and uptake of diagnostic COVID-19 testing in underserved, COVID-19 medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable populations

The T&E team employs the core components of the Translational Science Benefits (TSBM) Model¹ to assess the translation of innovation related to COVID-19 testing into clinical applications, healthcare guidelines, community interventions, policies, and other outcomes that benefit underserved communities at large.

Key Benefits

CLINICAL

COVID-19 Diagnostic procedures.

Testing diagnostic services performed for individuals in the community to diagnose COVID-19.

COMMUNITY

Community Health Services.

Community members and org's working together to provide COVID-19 services to the community to increase access to and uptake of COVID-19 testing.

COMMUNITY

Health Education Resources. Tailored resources that inform community members of COVID-19 benefits and risks through targeted delivery.

COMMUNITY

Testing Accessibility. Equity and ability for all to gain entry to and to receive COVID-19 testing services

ECONOMIC

Cost Savings. Reduced financial costs of COVID-19 testing services by providing free COVID-19 testing and distributing free at-home test kits and preventative supplies to communities.

The team

Tracking & Evaluation team: G, Dave Tara Carr, Shelly Maras, Valerie Lucas, Taylor Baldwin, Jade Hollars, Rossana Roberts

C2G Program Administration Team:

Find out more: <https://radx-up.org/grants/community-collaboration/>
<https://radx-up.org/about/coordination-center/tracking-evaluation-cdcc-radxup/>

RADx-UP Community Collaboration Grant Program: A Summary of TSBM Outcomes

The Community Collaboration Grant Program (C2G) has funded 69 projects across seven cycles.

Translational Science Benefits Model¹

IMPACT PROFILE

Key Benefits: An In-Depth Look

The figure below illustrates the TSBM Indicators¹ and the number of projects by cycle with which their outcomes correspond with.

Project Outcomes Mapped to TSBM Key Benefit Areas (n= 22 projects)

Increase capacity for COVID-19 rapid testing in the Knoxville community by 60 no-appointment tests each week.

Establish a call center and provide bilingual staff to attend all the calls and texts received by community members requesting information or appointments for COVID-19 testing or vaccines

Distribute safety kits including disinfectant wipes, gloves, masks, hand soap and hand sanitizer to over 500 hundred individuals and families.

Advocate in City Hall for a surge plan and the implementation of a wastewater track.

Hire and train staff to meet extended hours for COVID-19 testing site. (2 staff members worked extended hours to provide COVID-19 test, 7 individuals were trained to do COVID-19 testing at the Open Door free clinic).

Trained 13 Latinx community leaders, 10 youth fellows, and several staff members on COVID-19 outreach and education, and in the use of COVID-19 test kits.